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**RELATIONS OF REPRESENTATIVES OF TRANSOXIANA IN SAMARRA
DURING THE REIGNS OF THE CALIPHS AL-MUTAWAKKIL (847-861)
AND AL-MUNTAŞIR (861-862)**

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Abstract.

The article examines the relations of representatives of Transoxiana in Samarra during the reigns of the Abbasid caliphs al-Mutawakkil (847-861) and al-Muntaşir (861-862). Particular attention is paid to the role of Turkic ghilman, the Faraghina, the Ushrusanians, and other people originating from the eastern regions of the caliphate in the political life of Samarra in the mid-ninth century. Drawing on the accounts of al-Ṭabarī, al-Ya‘qūbī, and al-Mas‘ūdī, the article analyzes the circumstances of the crisis of 861, the assassination of al-Mutawakkil, and the growing influence of military corps over the order of succession. It argues that the representatives of Transoxiana did not constitute a single political grouping, but acted within a complex system of patronage ties, military interests, and court rivalry. A separate place is given to the socio-spatial dimension of the problem: archaeological and topographical studies of Samarra, especially the works of A. Northedge and M. Gordon, allow the city to be viewed not only as the capital of the Abbasid Caliphate but also as a space of settlement and competition among different military corps. The article concludes that the Samarran crisis marked an important stage in the weakening of Abbasid central authority and, at the same time, revealed the increased role of people from Transoxiana and neighboring regions in the military-political system of the caliphate.

Keywords: Abbasid Caliphate, Samarra, al-Mutawakkil, al-Muntaşir, Samarran anarchy, Transoxiana, Faraghina, Turkic ghilman, Ushrusanians, military corps, al-Ṭabarī, al-Ya‘qūbī, al-Mas‘ūdī, A. Northedge, M. Gordon.

The reign of al-Mutawakkil (847-861) and the subsequent short rule of his son al-Muntaşir (861-862) belong to those periods of Abbasid history in which the internal logic of power becomes especially visible. Samarra, conceived under al-Mu'tasim as a new military capital, had by the mid-ninth century ceased to be merely the caliph's residence and a place where the army was stationed. It had turned into a complex political space in which the interests of the court, Turkic military groupings, men from Fergana and other regions of Transoxiana, as well as various ethnic and service corps, came into conflict. In this context, the assassination of al-Mutawakkil in 861 cannot be reduced to an ordinary palace conspiracy. It became the outward manifestation of a deeper crisis of caliphal authority, which modern historiography usually associates with the beginning of the so-called "Sammarran anarchy" - a period marked by the sharp weakening of the institution of the caliphate and the strengthening of military factions [6; pp. 196-205].

The significance of this topic is not limited to the importance of Samarra for the political history of the Abbasid Caliphate. The events of 850-862 also reveal another process: the incorporation of people from Transoxiana into the military and administrative structures of the Islamic empire. The Turkic ghilman were warriors of slave or dependent status; the Faraghina, that is, men from Fergana, appear in the sources as a distinct military group; and the Ushrusanians were connected with the region of Ushrusana, situated between Samarkand and Fergana. These groups could act side by side, enter into situational alliances, and depend on the same court mechanisms, yet their legal status, origin, military functions, and political interests did not fully coincide.

This article analyzes the relations of representatives of Transoxiana in Samarra under al-Mutawakkil and al-Muntaşir and identifies the forms of their cooperation, rivalry, and participation in the crisis of caliphal authority in 850-862. To this end, several interconnected questions are addressed: how Arabic chronicles describe the events in Samarra during this period; what role ethnic and regional military corps played in al-Mutawakkil's policy; how Turkic military groups, the Faraghina, and other

people from Transoxiana became involved in the conspiracy of 861; to what extent archaeological evidence concerning the layout of Samarra clarifies the testimony of written sources; and, finally, what significance the Samarran crisis had for the later history of the Abbasid Caliphate and Transoxiana.

The historiography of the problem developed gradually and along several lines of inquiry. H. Kennedy treats the Abbasid army not as a simple military mechanism but as a socio-political institution. In his interpretation, the ethnic corps of Samarra were not only battlefield forces but also independent factors in political decision-making [6; pp. 185-205]. M. Gordon, who specifically studied the Turkic military elite of Samarra, convincingly shows that the Turkic commanders did not constitute a single “national party.” Their milieu rather resembled a system of competing patronage groups linked to the court, the treasury, salaries, and the distribution of grants [5; pp. 75-85]. This conclusion requires greater caution toward any simplified schemes in which the Turks, the Faraghina, and other eastern corps are portrayed as a single political bloc.

A special place belongs to the work of A. Northedge, who moved the discussion of the Samarran crisis from the sphere of purely political history into the field of historical topography. His analysis of quarters, palaces, roads, and military settlements demonstrates that the structure of power in Samarra had a concrete spatial expression [7; pp. 45-60]. In other words, the struggle for influence unfolded not in an abstract “palace environment” but in a city where the location of troops, the proximity of the corps to the caliphal residence, and the organization of urban zones themselves became political factors. For understanding the origin and status of people from Fergana, the article by C. E. Bosworth in the *Encyclopaedia Iranica* remains important: it presents Fergana as a region with long-standing military and political traditions, incorporated into the Islamic world not merely as an eastern periphery but also as a source of military personnel and elite service groups [4; pp. 293-297].

Among the written testimonies concerning the final years of al-Mutawakkil’s reign and the first months of al-Muntaṣir’s rule, the chronicle of al-Ṭabarī occupies a central place. Volume XXXIV of the English translation, *The History of al-Ṭabarī*:

Incipient Decline, presents a coherent account of the crisis of 861. Al-Tabari describes the growing tension between al-Mutawakkil and his son al-Muntaṣir, shows the role of the Turkic military, and records the circumstances of the caliph's assassination [1; pp. 160-180]. The strength of this source lies in the density of its political narrative. Al-Tabari records not only the fact of a violent transfer of power, but also the anxious atmosphere of palace confrontation in which personal relations within the Abbasid dynasty could no longer be separated from the interests of military groupings.

It would, however, be methodologically risky to read al-Ṭabarī as an impartial record of events. His narrative is arranged in annalistic form and goes back to transmitters whose reports may have reflected the positions of Baghdadi, Samarran, or court circles. The chronicle is therefore especially valuable for reconstructing the sequence of events, but it requires caution when the motives of the participants in the conspiracy are discussed. In describing the assassination of al-Mutawakkil, al-Ṭabarī in fact brings to the surface three lines of conflict at once: the dynastic conflict between the caliph and al-Muntaṣir; the military conflict between the caliph and the Turkic commanders; and the institutional conflict between the idea of the caliph's sacred authority and the court's actual dependence on the army [1; pp. 160-180].

Al-Yaqubi presents the events much more briefly and without the level of detail characteristic of al-Ṭabarī. Yet this concision does not make his testimony secondary. His chronicle conveys the general picture of the weakening of central authority and the growing importance of military groups in Samarra. Unlike al-Ṭabarī, al-Ya'qūbī pays less attention to palace conspiracies; he is more interested in the place of these events within the broader course of Abbasid history. For the comparison of sources, this perspective is particularly useful, because it allows us to see not only the episode of 861 but also its political background.

Al-Masudi, writing later, represents another type of historical testimony. His *Murūj al-dhahab* cannot be treated as a simple chronicle of the events of 861. It is a historical and literary work in which political narrative is combined with reflections on power, morals, and the fate of dynasties. For the study of Samarra, this perspective has

independent value: al-Mas'ūdī helps us see the crisis not only as a change of ruler but also as a sign of a deeper disintegration of the political order. At the same time, the retrospective character of his account must be taken into consideration: the author wrote at a time when the consequences of the Samarran crisis had already become historically evident.

A comparison of al-Ṭabarī, al-Ya'qūbī, and al-Mas'ūdī reveals one significant feature of the source base. Arabic chronicles primarily record the actions of elites - the caliph, heirs, military commanders, and courtiers. Everyday relations among different Central Asian groups remain on the margins of their attention. For this reason, the links and conflicts among the Turkic ghilman, the Faraghina, and the Ushrusanians have to be reconstructed indirectly: through their participation in military corps, systems of settlement, patronage ties, involvement in conspiracies, and reactions to changes in the order of succession.

Al-Mutawakkil came to power at a moment when the Turkic military elite had already become firmly embedded in Abbasid politics. Under al-Mu'taṣim and al-Wāthiq, Samarra served not simply as the ruler's new residence; it became an instrument for managing the army. The transfer of military groups from Baghdad to a specially organized space did indeed reduce tension between the troops and the population of the old capital. Paradoxically, however, this same decision generated a new problem: the army found itself physically close to the caliph, the palace, and the centers of decision-making. Samarra strengthened authority and, at the same time, undermined its foundations.

Al-Mutawakkil sought to restore the prestige of caliphal authority and to restrict the autonomy of military commanders. He redistributed influence among groups, undertook large-scale palace construction, changed the courtly and religious orientation of power, and attempted to influence the order of succession. In the military sphere, this policy did not imply the destruction of ethnic corps. Rather, the caliph tried to keep them within a system of mutual balance. It is precisely here that the Turks, the Faraghina, the Ushrusanians, and the Maghāriba acquire special significance.

The most influential military stratum in Samarra remained the Turkic ghilman. Their position was determined not by military training alone. They had access to the caliph, the treasury, and the system of appointments, and in the conditions of Samarran politics this meant a great deal. At the same time, the Turkic commanders did not form a monolithic community. They were connected by personal obligations, rivalries, court alliances, and competition for influence over the heirs. As M. Gordon rightly shows, the Turkic military milieu of Samarra is more accurately viewed as a complex system of commanders and clienteles, rather than as a homogeneous ethnic bloc [5; pp. 75-85].

The Faraghina, men from Fergana, occupied a different position. They came from a region which, even before its final incorporation into the Islamic political system, possessed its own traditions of military organization and maintained contacts with neighboring powers. Bosworth emphasizes the importance of Fergana as a major area of eastern Transoxiana, connected with the routes between the Syr Darya, Samarkand, and the eastern regions [4; pp. 293-297]. In the Samarran context, the Faraghina cannot be mechanically identified with Turkic slave-soldiers. Their origin, social status, and modes of incorporation into service could differ. They stood alongside the Turks and interacted with them, but retained the features of a distinct regional military group.

The Ushrusanians constituted another significant element of the Central Asian presence in Samarra. Ushrusana, located between Samarkand and Fergana, had a complex history of local rulers, dihqan nobility, and gradual integration into the Islamic political system. In the Abbasid army, men from Ushrusana could act both as warriors and as representatives of a local elite connected with the eastern provinces of the caliphate. Their significance was not limited to their numbers. They formed part of a wider network of eastern Iranian and Turkic service groups through which Transoxiana became increasingly involved in the political life of the caliphate.

The Maghāriba did not belong to Transoxiana, yet within the Samarran system they performed an important balancing function. Their presence shows that Samarra was not a “Turkic city” in the narrow sense. It was a polyethnic military capital where

different corps were settled, received pay, entered into competition, and sought access to political resources. H. Kennedy emphasizes that the ethnic corps of Samarra became an institutional feature of the Abbasid army in the ninth century; their political importance increased precisely because caliphal authority became ever more dependent on their loyalty [6; pp. 185-195].

Al-Mutawakkil's policy revealed the main contradiction of the Samarran system: the caliph sought to strengthen central authority but could not dispense with the military groups on which the security of the regime rested. Any redistribution of influence between heirs or commanders affected already established patronage ties and was perceived as a threat. The conflict over succession therefore quickly moved beyond a family affair of the Abbasids. For the military factions, it became a matter of status, access to resources, and political survival.

The assassination of al-Mutawakkil in 861 was one of those events after which the previous order could no longer be restored in its earlier form. Al-Tabari presents the episode as the result of growing tension between the caliph, his son al-Muntaşir, and military circles, above all the Turkic commanders [1; pp. 160-180]. On the surface, the conflict concerned the question of succession. According to the sources, al-Mutawakkil increasingly inclined in favor of another son, al-Mu'tazz, thereby weakening the position of al-Muntaşir. Yet dynastic competition by itself does not explain the scale of the crisis. What made it dangerous was something else: behind each possible heir there could stand different court groups, military commanders, and the clientele linked to them.

The Turkic commanders had concrete reasons to fear al-Mutawakkil's policy. The caliph sought to strengthen control over the army, redistribute influence at court, and probably change the existing order of access to grants and offices. For the military elite of Samarra, this meant not an abstract political change but a direct threat to their established position. In such a situation, the alliance of part of the Turkic military with al-Muntaşir appeared to be a pragmatic decision. The heir obtained armed support,

while the commanders gained an opportunity to remove a ruler whose policy was becoming increasingly unacceptable to them.

The role of representatives of Central Asia in these events requires especially careful analysis. Not all “eastern” or “Turkic” military men of Samarra possessed the same status, and to merge them into a single group would be methodologically incorrect. The Turkic ghilman were connected with the institution of military dependence and court service. The Faraghina, originating from Fergana, could function as a distinct regional military group, but their social position did not necessarily coincide with that of slave guards. The Ushrusanians also preserved their own specificity: they were linked to Transoxiana and the eastern Iranian milieu. The issue, therefore, is not a single “Central Asian party,” but intersecting networks of people from the eastern regions of the caliphate whose interests, at a particular moment, could coincide with those of the Turkic commanders.

The brief reign of al-Muntaṣir did not bring stabilization. On the contrary, it revealed the weakness of the very structure of power that had emerged after the removal of al-Mutawakkil. The new caliph depended on the forces that had helped him take the throne. The question of succession remained open and painful: al-Mu‘tazz and al-Mu‘ayyad retained significance as potential centers of alternative legitimacy. Al-Muntasir’s policy was directed toward neutralizing the threat posed by his brothers, but this course only made the dependence of caliphal authority on military decisions even more visible.

The “Samarran anarchy” should therefore not be reduced to a sequence of palace coups. It was a crisis of the very mechanism of supreme power. Whereas the army had earlier acted as an instrument of the caliph, the caliph now increasingly became a figure through whom the army legitimized its own decisions. H. Kennedy connects the beginning of the Samarran crisis precisely with the fact that ethnic corps and military commanders acquired the ability to intervene in the order of succession and, in practice, to determine the fate of caliphs [6; pp. 196-205].

The participation of Central Asian elements in this process had a dual character. On the one hand, men from Transoxiana and neighboring regions strengthened the military potential of the Abbasid Caliphate. Their service demonstrated the empire's capacity to use the resources of the eastern provinces and to incorporate their representatives into the most important structures of power. On the other hand, the concentration of such groups in Samarra created a new political environment in which regional and ethnic corps gradually became independent participants in the struggle for influence. Their loyalty depended not only on dynastic or religious ideology. It was also shaped by salaries, land grants, relations with commanders, access to the caliph, and prospects for advancement at court.

The conflict of 861 was not a "revolt of the representatives of Transoxiana" against the Abbasids. Such an interpretation would distort the nature of the events. What we see is an internal crisis of the Abbasid military system, in which representatives of Transoxiana occupied a visible but not isolated position. Their actions were determined not by regional separatism but by the logic of Samarran politics - the struggle for access to the caliph, the treasury, heirs, command positions, and patronage resources.

Written sources provide the researcher with the sequence of events, but they reveal little of Samarra as a living social space. They tell us about caliphs, heirs, commanders, and conspiracies, while the city itself often remains merely a background. It is precisely here that archaeological and topographical studies acquire special value. A. Northedge showed that Samarra was not a spontaneous military camp that had grown up around the court, but a carefully organized capital with palaces, avenues, mosques, military quarters, and zones of settlement for various groups [7; pp. 45-60].

The city's topography helps explain why the military corps were able to become an independent political force so quickly. They were not located somewhere on the periphery of the caliphate and did not function as a remote provincial army. On the contrary, they lived in the capital itself, close to the palace and to the centers of decision-making. This spatial proximity changed everything. Military quarters, roads, palace complexes, and settlement zones created an environment in which the

mobilization of an armed group could almost immediately affect the situation at court. The conspiracy of 861 cannot be explained by political dissatisfaction alone. It was also made possible by the very structure of Samarra as a military capital.

Northedge convincingly shows that the layout of Samarra reflected the separation of service groups and administrative functions. The Faraghina, the Turks, the Ushrusanians, and other groups existed not only as ethnonyms or conventional labels in the chronicles. They were social collectives incorporated into a concrete urban space. Of course, archaeology does not always allow us to determine with complete certainty which particular quarter belonged to which group. Such precision would be methodologically risky. Yet the general conclusion is sufficiently clear: Samarra was a city of a segmented military elite, where the spatial placement of groups reflected the political and social structure of power [7; pp. 45-60].

In this context, the works of M. Gordon are particularly useful. They make it possible to connect the topographical picture with political history. If Northedge shows the material structure of the city, Gordon helps us understand how Turkic amirs, the Faraghina, and other military groups acted within that structure. In his interpretation, the Samarran army cannot be reduced to a simple “army of the caliph.” What we have before us is a system of corps, each with its own connections, commanders, interests, and channels of access to power [5; pp. 75-85].

Modern projects for documenting archaeological heritage, including EAMENA, develop this approach at a new technical level. Their contribution does not lie in providing new details about the conspiracy of 861. Such information is still supplied primarily by written sources. The importance of EAMENA and similar projects lies elsewhere: they make it possible to record more precisely the condition of the Samarran landscape and to compare historical maps, satellite data, and traces of construction [8]. For Samarra this is especially significant, since it is a vast archaeological complex exposed to destruction, modern construction, and landscape change. Methodologically, these data adjust the viewpoint of the chroniclers: al-Ṭabarī, al-Ya‘qūbī, and al-Mas‘ūdī focus on caliphs and commanders, whereas archaeology brings back into the

field of analysis the urban environment in which those commanders lived, moved, and acted.

Archaeology does not replace the written tradition. It forces us to read it more carefully. Samarran politics appears not only as a struggle among people and groups but also as a struggle embedded in the space of the city. The palace, military quarters, roads, and settlement zones formed an infrastructure of political pressure and, in extreme cases, political violence. The events of 861 therefore unfolded not in an abstract “palace environment,” but in a concrete urban system in which the architecture of power and military organization were closely connected.

Conclusion

The relations of representatives of Transoxiana in Samarra under al-Mutawakkil and al-Muntaşir were far more complex than they may appear from a superficial reading of the chronicles. The sources do not provide grounds for speaking of a single Central Asian grouping acting according to a common regional plan. Such a scheme would be too linear. It is more accurate to distinguish several intersecting groups: the Turkic ghilman, the Faraghina, the Ushrusanians, and other people from the eastern regions of the caliphate. They could cooperate, compete, enter into temporary alliances, and diverge in their interests depending on the specific political situation.

Under al-Mutawakkil, central authority attempted to restore control over the military corps, but the paradox lay in the fact that the security of the regime itself depended precisely on those corps. The caliph sought to strengthen the throne, yet he could not dispense with forces that were increasingly interfering in court politics. The assassination of al-Mutawakkil in 861 demonstrated this dependence with particular clarity: the military groups of Samarra no longer merely protected authority; they could also decide the fate of the ruler himself. Under al-Muntaşir the situation did not change. On the contrary, the caliph’s dependence on military decisions became an even more obvious basis of the political order.

The historical significance of these processes manifested itself in several directions. The Samarran crisis accelerated the weakening of Abbasid central authority and

prepared the way for the further fragmentation of the caliphate. It revealed the increased role of military elites of eastern origin, including people from Transoxiana and Fergana. Finally, it consolidated a dangerous model in which caliphal legitimacy increasingly required the support of military corps, while the army gradually turned into an independent political arbiter.

For the history of Central Asia, the participation of the Faraghina, the Ushrusanians, and Turkic military men in Samarran politics has special significance. It shows that Transoxiana and neighboring regions were not a passive periphery of the Abbasid world. Their representatives entered the military and political structures of the caliphate, took part in court conflicts, and influenced the fate of central authority. This was not national representation in the modern sense, but military service, patronage, the struggle for resources, access to the caliph, and participation in the complex system of Samarran politics.

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